

An Economic Analysis of Tobacco Consumption

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As a consequence of industrialization and urbanization, smoking has become a serious health issue worldwide. Studies have found that smoking can increase the risk of stroke and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease by 40-50% [1]. Smokers are about three times more likely to suffer from coronary heart disease and lung cancer than non-smokers [1]. Each year, smoking-induced diseases are responsible for five million deaths [2]. Worse still, at least twelve people die in every one minute, and one out of six NCD related deaths are attributable to smoking [1].

The increase in prevalence of smoking is a serious public health challenge in both developed and developing countries. World Health Organization estimated that smoking-induced mortality would reach ten million by 2030 [2]. Smoking is responsible for 71% of lung cancer, 42% of chronic respiratory disease and 10% of cardiovascular disease yearly [2]. In fact, the burden attributable to smoking is more serious in developing countries than in developed countries with an estimated 70-80% of smokers and smoking related deaths are from developing countries [2-4]. Smoking also causes serious negative impacts on children health [2]. About half of the children worldwide live in smoke-polluted environment, and around two hundred thousand pass away annually due to second hand smoke [2].

One of the reasons causing the prevalence of smoking to increase alarmingly is that people do not understand the role of economics in smoking. Economics has a strong but often neglected influence on smoking, given that it can affect the 'incentive' and 'disincentive' encountered by individuals indirectly when individuals are making decisions to smoke. Economics can also provide individuals with a useful framework for identifying the factors that can affect their decision to smoke. Hence, it is important for researchers and policy makers to have a better understanding of how economics explain smoking.

In order to understand the influence of economics on smoking, one should have a basic knowledge of microeconomic theory. According to the economic perspective, individuals tend to behave rationally to produce optimal outcomes by maximizing the benefits received from consuming market goods and services, while minimizing the incurred costs. Rational individuals consider

the costs and benefits of smoking, and smoke only when the net benefits received are positive, i.e. benefits are more than costs.

The costs of smoking, including both monetary and non-monetary, are the price of tobacco and the harmful effects on health, whereas the benefits are the pleasures that smoking produces. These costs and benefits are known as personal costs (PC) and personal benefits (PB). Hence, rational individuals will tend to maximize the total net benefits received from smoking by equalizing their personal marginal costs (PMC) and personal marginal benefits (PMB) (i.e. $PMC = PMB$). PMC refers to the additional costs borne by individuals when consuming an additional unit of tobacco. PMB, on the other hand, refers to the additional benefits received by individuals when consuming an additional unit of tobacco.

Since smoking involves costs of participation, PMC increases with every additional unit of tobacco consumed, i.e. positively correlated with tobacco consumption. Conversely, however, owing to the law of diminishing returns, PMB decreases with every additional unit of tobacco consumed, i.e. negatively correlated with tobacco consumption. Based on cost-benefit marginal analysis, it can be concluded that rational individuals will smoke only when their PMB is greater than their PMC.

Economics can explain the high prevalence of smoking in the present society in several ways. First, the adverse effects of smoking on health only become apparent when a serious deterioration in health occurs, meaning that individuals will only realize the costs of smoking in the future when they age. This indicates a lag between realization of the costs of smoking and participation in smoking. Hence, individuals, especially those who are more present oriented are more likely to smoke, and only avoid smoking when their health and well-being are seriously affected.

Second, smokers often do not realize that smoking can cause serious negative externalities to the society, such as, second-hand smoke and environmental pollution. This means that smoking also involves social costs (SC), which the costs are borne by the society as a whole. Since SC is difficult to measure and observe, individuals tend to underestimate the actual costs of smoking, which means that the PMC of smoking is lower than the social

marginal costs (SMC). This will, in turn, result in overconsumption of tobacco.

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Yong Kang CHEAH was born in Penang, Malaysia in October 1985. He obtained his Ph.D. degree from University of Malaya, Malaysia and Master's and Bachelor's degree from Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia. His field of research is in Health Economics, Public Health and Consumer Behavior. His works have been published in numerous refereed journals, such as, Hitotsubashi Journal of Economics, Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention, Malaysian Journal of Medical Sciences, Malaysian Journal of Nutrition and Malaysian Journal of Economics Studies.